

This is a step-by-step illustration on how to run source code from version 1.0.

If you find codes cannot run on your end, you are welcome to share error details on https://github.com/HAN-2/MOIST_ERRORS/issues or send an email to haf033@usask.ca (Han).

I will help to debug and thank you for your interest!

Step 1. Download any documents or “download all”. The “Long term test ” was used as an example here.

Files

Name	Size	
Files (499.0 kB)		Download all
Long term test.rar md5:23ad2cdede0ecb5a66bf2ede4bb0f89e	429.2 kB	Download
MOIST_segreated_version.rar md5:ea08c064419417cba9c51100d4f158de	22.3 kB	Download
Semi-analytical test (saturated and isothermal conditions).rar md5:30172600ab958798444de3300f1ca6f3	16.0 kB	Download
Semi-analytical test (unsaturated and non-isothermal).rar md5:7e8989927347ac37b6f56c71101546	16.6 kB	Download
thoritical_test.rar md5:66e3883d36be15e9c3f9837d54f3469c	14.9 kB	Download

Step 2. After downloading, decompress the “.rar” then all included scripts should be available as shown in step 3.

Name	Date modified	Type	Size
Today			
Long term test.rar	2024-09-12 2:37 PM	WinRAR 压缩文件	420 KB
Yesterday			
Last month			
Earlier this year			

Step 3. Copy the path of this folder. Mine is “C:\Users\Han\Downloads\Long term test”

Step 4. Paste to MATLAB and locate the folder:

Step 5. Open the “Main_program_2.m” (“Main_program.m” in other examples) and click Run:

The screenshot displays the MATLAB software interface. At the top, the 'Run' button is circled in red. Below it, the code editor window shows the following MATLAB code:

```
1 clear all
2 global out_X out_X1 out_X4 out_X3 out_X2 surface_flag
3
4 Initial_condition=readmatrix("stumpp","Range",'A:F',"Sheet","Initial_condition");
5 Rain_record=readmatrix("stumpp","Range",'A:C',"Sheet","Rain_record");
6 Daily_climate_record=readmatrix("stumpp","Range",'A:M',"Sheet","Daily_climate_record");
7 IVA_array=readmatrix("stumpp","Range",'A:C',"Sheet","Rainfall_isotope");
8 scalingfactor = Initial_condition (:,end);
9 mea = readmatrix("stumpp","Range",'B:E',"Sheet","result");
10
11 X5ip1=struct('Rain_record',Rain_record,'Daily_climate_record',Daily_climate_record);
12
13 pTest = 6;
14 poi = [30;90];
15 hcria = -1000;
16 bottom_condition = 1;
17 iso_spe = 0; % 1 is H and 0 is O
18 itm = 0;
19
20 %----- Time information
21 tMax = 1735*86400;
22
23 %----- Space information
24 L =1.51;
25 dz =0.01;
26 z = dz/2:dz:L;
27 n = length(z);
28 sii = 0;
29 bc = 0;
30
```

At the bottom, the Command Window shows the prompt `f>>`.

Step 6. A progress percentage will appear to the command window:

The screenshot displays the MATLAB environment. At the top, a toolbar includes buttons for 'Run', 'Section Break', 'Run and Advance', 'Run to End', 'Pause', 'Step', and 'Stop'. Below the toolbar, the 'Editor' window shows the code for 'Main_program_2.m' with the following content:

```
1 clear all
2 global out_X out_X1 out_X4 out_X3 out_X2 surface_flag
3
4 Initial_condition=readmatrix("stump", "Range", 'A:F', "Sheet", "Initial_condition");
5 Rain_record=readmatrix("stump", "Range", 'A:C', "Sheet", "Rain_record");
6 Daily_climate_record=readmatrix("stump", "Range", 'A:M', "Sheet", "Daily_climate_record");
7 IVA_array=readmatrix("stump", "Range", 'A:C', "Sheet", "Rainfall_isotope");
8 scalingfactor = Initial_condition (:,end);
9 mea = readmatrix("stump", "Range", 'B:E', "Sheet", "result");
10
11 X5ip1=struct('Rain_record',Rain_record,'Daily_climate_record',Daily_climate_record);
12
13 pTest = 6;
14 poi = [30;90];
15 hcria = -1000;
16 bottom_condition = 1;
17 iso_spe = 0; % 1 is H and 0 is O
18 itm = 0;
19
20 %----- Time information
21 tMax = 1735*86400;
22
23 %----- Space information
24 L =1.51;
25 dz =0.01;
26 z = dz/2:dz:L;
27 n = length(z);
28 sii = 0;
29 bc = 0;
30
```

Below the code editor, the 'Command Window' shows the execution progress:

```
>> Main_program_2
0.54755
```

The value '0.54755' is circled in red, indicating the current progress percentage of the execution.

Step 7, After this number reaching 100, the outputs will appear in the workspace:

Workspace

Name	Value
ig	152x1 double
R	8.3140
R1	1
R11	1
R111	1
Rain_record	1736x3 double
redo	0
rho	1000
root_flag	1
S	151x1 double
sat_flag	1
scalingfactor	151x1 double
si1	8
South	'North'
surface_flag	0
T	151x1 double
T0	151x1 double
t_test	149990400
theta	151x1 double
theta0	151x1 double
theta1	151x1 double
theta_	151x1 double
tMax	149990400
total_gwep	0
total_rain	0
tspan	[149947200,149990...
tt	22x1 double
variable_Pt	1
X	1x1 struct
X2	1x1 struct
X4	1x1 struct
X5ip1	1x1 struct
X5ip2	1x1 struct
X5ip2_update	1x1 struct
X5op	1x1 struct
y	22x604 double
y0	604x1 double
z	1x151 double
z_cil	151x1736 double
z_cils	1x2473 double
z_cim	151x1736 double
z_dt	3473x1 double
z_h	151x1736 double
z_q	152x3473 double
z_qf	152x3473 double
z_qfz	152x3473 double
z_qfs	3473x1 double
z_rain	3473x1 double
z_T	151x1736 double
z_theta	151x1736 double
zoh	0
zom	0
zT	2
zu	10
zz_cil	151x3473 double
zz_h	151x3473 double
zz_sink	151x3473 double
zz_theta	151x3473 double

Editor - C:\Users\Han\Downloads\Long term test\Main_program_2.m

```

424 %
227 %
zz_sink(1:n,i) = out_X1.sink;
228 %
zz_cil(1:n,i) = (cil./1000.*0.018./0.02-out_X4.ref)/out_X4.ref*1000;
229 %
z_cils(1,i) = (out_X1.cils./1000.*0.018./0.02-out_X4.ref)/out_X4.ref*1000;
230 %
231 %-----Time Display-----%
232 dispTime=num2str(t_test/tMax*100);
233 fprintf(repmat('\b',1,si1));
234 sii=fprintf(dispTime);
235 out_X=X;
236 dt = dt_initial*1;
237 %
238 %
239 if any(theta>0.99*X2.theta_sat(n,1))%any(h>X2.he)%any(theta == X2.theta_sat)
sat_flag = 1;
dt = 86400/2;
240 %
241 %
242 else
sat_flag = 0;
dt = dt_initial;
243 %
244 end
245 %
246 options = odeset(options,'InitialStep', dt, 'MaxStep',dt);
247 Delta=(cil./1000.*0.018./0.02-out_X4.ref)/out_X4.ref*1000;
248 if CalTT>tMax
break
249 %
250 end
251 end
252 plot(z_cil(end,:))
253 hold on
254 scatter(meas(:,1),meas(:,2))
255 plot(meas(:,3),meas(:,4))

```

Command Window

```

>> Main_program_2
fx 100.0576>>

```

For example, z_theta has 151*1736, meaning that it contains soil water profile of each day (1736 days in total); Similarly, z_cil contains the soil water isotopic composition values.